

Our precious open data: the MAPPALab framework for open archaeological data

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Abstract. Archaeological excavations irrevocably alter stratigraphy, so documentation and preservation of datasets are vital. Digital ‘datafication’ with open-data standards enables transparent, reproducible reuse. The MAPPALab laboratory at the University of Pisa developed a FAIR-compliant ecosystem: MOD, Italy’s first open repository with DOIs, open licences and Dublin Core metadata; ALD, an open data journal; and MAGOH, a platform providing georeferenced archaeological data from 103 Tuscan municipalities.

Conference Themes: Open Infrastructures for Responsible Research Assessment

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1 Main Contribution

Archaeology is inherently destructive: each excavation irreversibly alters the stratigraphic contexts providing information on past societies and environments. Consequently, documentation and the generation, aggregation and preservation of heterogeneous datasets, from stratigraphic trenches, systematic surveys or material characterisation, are essential and cannot be revisited. Once confined to analogue archives, these records were largely inaccessible until a digital revolution and “datafication” enabled integration, sharing and reuse [1, 2]. By adopting open-data standards, researchers ensure that reinterpretations remain transparent, reproducible and adaptable to evolving theoretical and methodological frameworks [3]. In Italy, entrenched cultural attitudes and institutional incentives favouring high-impact publications over open datasets continue to hinder progress. In response, the MAPPALab (digital Methodologies APPLIED to Archaeology) laboratory [4] at the University of Pisa has developed an integrated digital ecosystem fully aligned with FAIR principles. Central is the MOD (Mappa Open Data) portal [5], the first open-access repository in

Italy for archaeological research data and grey literature. Hosted on Fedora Commons within the University's Digital Library, MOD assigns DOIs to all records, excavation reports, high-resolution photographs, 3D models, GIS layers, typological databases and archaeometric analysis ensuring preservation, citation and reuse under CC BY or CC BY-SA licences. All entries use Dublin Core metadata in open, machine-readable formats (XML, JSON, CSV), facilitating interoperability with external systems and accessibility for stakeholders. To enrich semantic coherence, MOD is transitioning to the Ariadne AO-Cat ontology, fostering Linked Open Data environments [6]. This infrastructure is supported by policies on intellectual property, privacy, attribution and licensing, while transparent governance and workflows ensure sustainability and collaboration. MAPPALab established ALD (ArcheoLogica Data) [7], an open-access, peer-reviewed journal dedicated to archaeological datasets, typological catalogues and methodological reports. All articles are free, DOI-enabled and integrated with MOD, enhancing attribution, visibility and impact. The MAGOH (Managing Archaeological data for a sustainable GOVERNANCE of the Heritage) portal [8] publishes vectorised and georeferenced records from 103 Tuscan municipalities. By converting grey and white literature into Linked Open Data, MAGOH enables spatial analysis, broadens public and scholarly access to regional archaeological documentation and secures artifact preservation even without physical specimens and ongoing development.

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